

Polarographic Study of Cd(II)-Oxalate- β -Picoline Mixed System

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Mixed complexes of Cd(II) with oxalate (Ox^{2-}) and β -picoline (Pico) have been studied polarographically at constant ionic strength [$\mu=2.0$ (NaNO_3)] and at constant pH 8. The reduction of the complexes at d.m.e. is reversible and diffusion controlled. Three mixed complexes, $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pico})]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pico})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{Pico})]^{2-}$ are formed. Their overall stability constants at 25° are $\log \beta_{11}=4.1$, $\log \beta_{12}=4.95$ and $\log \beta_{21}=4.84$, respectively.

LITERATURE reveals that simple complexes of Cd(II) with oxalate¹⁻⁵ or β -picoline⁶ have been studied polarographically but the mixed complexes with these ligands have not been studied so far. The present study was undertaken with this end in view.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The ionic strength was maintained constant at $\mu=2.0$ using NaNO_3 as supporting electrolyte. β -Picoline and potassium oxalate were used as ligands. The concentration of Cd(II) was kept at $1 \times 10^{-5} M$. Polarograms were obtained by means of a manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer (PL 50). Purified hydrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. All measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 2.0 M NaNO_3 , open circuit): $m=3.98$ mg/sec, $t=2.2$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.9$ $\text{mg}^{2/3} \text{sec}^{-1/6}$, $h_{\text{corr}}=39$ cm.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of Cd(II) in oxalate and β -picoline separately was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ vs $E_{\text{d.e.}}$ were of the order of 32 ± 1 mV.

The depolarizer and ligands (oxalate and β -picoline) were taken in the ratio of 1 : 100 and the polarograms were taken at different pH values (adjusted by adding very dilute solutions of HCl or NaOH). It was found that the maximum shift (negative) occurred at pH 8 and hence this pH was chosen for the study. The ionic strength was kept at $\mu=2.0$ to facilitate the addition of larger concentrations of oxalate ion.

Stability constants of simple complexes of Cd(II) with oxalate and β -picoline were determined

separately prior to the study of mixed ligand system. Identical conditions were maintained in both the simple and mixed systems.

Cd(II)-oxalate system :

A series of polarograms were obtained at constant ionic strength $\mu=2$ and at constant pH 8. A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{Ox}^{2-}]$ was a smooth curve indicating the formation of successive complexes. DeFord and Hume⁷ method was applied for the determination of composition and stability constants of the complexes. An analysis of $F_1 [X]$ functions reveals the formation of three successive complexes, viz., $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})_3]^{4-}$ with stability constants, $\log \beta_{10}=2.9$, $\log \beta_{20}=4.00$ and $\log \beta_{30}=4.90$. These results compare fairly well with literature values^{1,2}.

Cd(II)- β -picoline system :

A series of polarograms were obtained at constant ionic strength $\mu=2$ and constant pH 8. As β -picoline is a base it gets protonated in aqueous medium according to equilibrium (i).

Since hydrogen bound (protonated) base does not enter into complexation, the amount of the "free base" (i.e., unprotonated) only has to be taken for the concentration of the ligand. This can be calculated from the pK_a value of the base as per the following equilibrium :

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{Pico}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{PicoH}^+]} \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

$$\text{or } \log [\text{Pico}] = \log [\text{PicoH}^+] + \text{pH} - \text{p}K_a \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

The pK_a value of β -picoline at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at $\mu=2.0$ has been determined by the titration method⁸ using glass electrode and has been found to be 6.0. Hence the present study has been carried out at constant pH 8, where all the ligand will obviously be in the unprotonated form.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ FUNCTIONS FOR Cd(II)-OXALATE- β -PICOLINE MIXED SYSTEM

 $[Cd^{2+}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 2.0$ (NaNO₃), Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; pH 8; $(E_{1/2})_s = -0.57 V$ vs (SCE)

$[Ox^{2-}]$ M	$-E_{1/2}$ V vs (SCE)	i_d (μA)	Slope (mV)	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^{-4}$
Series I : [Pico] = 0.10 M (fixed)							
0.02	0.612	11.0	32	27.23	—	—	—
0.05	0.630	10.8	33	112.56	—	—	—
0.10	0.648	9.9	33	498.54	48.85	—	—
0.20	0.666	9.8	33	2044.81	101.71	3.89	—
0.30	0.677	9.5	33	4963.64	165.12	4.50	9.9
0.40	0.686	9.5	33	10000.00	249.75	5.49	9.7
0.50	0.693	9.0	33	18197.01	363.74	6.68	9.7
0.60	0.698	8.4	33	28906.80	481.61	7.58	9.8
Series II : [Pico] = 0.20 M (fixed)							
0.02	0.622	9.7	32	60.77	—	—	—
0.05	0.634	9.2	33	163.88	—	—	—
0.10	0.656	9.0	33	938.64	90.86	—	—
0.2	0.672	8.8	31	3220.33	159.52	4.48	9.4
0.3	0.681	8.5	32	6842.27	227.08	5.24	8.8
0.4	0.689	8.3	33	13058.70	325.72	6.39	3.5
0.5	0.695	8.1	33	21345.17	426.30	7.13	9.1

A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [Pico]$ was a smooth curve thereby showing the formation of successive complexes. Three complexes viz., $[Cd(Pico)]^{2+}$, $[Cd(Pico)_2]^{2+}$ and $[Cd(Pico)_3]^{2+}$ with stability constants, $\log \beta_{01} = 1.20$, $\log \beta_{02} = 2.00$ and $\log \beta_{03} = 3.42$ are formed.

Cd(II)-oxalate- β -picoline system :

This system has been investigated at constant ionic strength $\mu = 2$. The concentration of Ox^{2-} was varied from 0 to 0.6 M, keeping [Pico] constant at 0.1 M. In each case the waves were diffusion-controlled and reversible. $E_{1/2}$ values were more negative than those obtained in the absence of β -picoline thereby showing the formation of mixed complexes. The system was repeated at another (0.2 M) concentration of β -picoline. The Schaap and McMasters¹ method was used for the determination of composition and stability constants of mixed complexes.

From the plots of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ ($X = Ox^{2-}$, $Y = Pico$) vs $[Ox^{2-}]$ at fixed [β -picoline] (0.1 M and 0.2 M)

following intercept values for constants¹ A, B, C and D have been obtained :

Series I : [Pico] = 0.1 M (fixed)

$\log A = 1$, $\log B = 3.48$, $\log C = 4.20$
and $\log D = 5.00$.

Series II : [Pico] = 0.2 M (fixed)

$\log A = 1.48$, $\log B = 3.85$, $\log C = 4.42$
and $\log D = 4.95$

The stability constants have been obtained from these constants. Three mixed complexes as noted below are formed.

$[Cd(Ox)(Pico)]$: $\log \beta_{11} = 4.1$

$[Cd(Ox)(Pico)_2]$: $\log \beta_{12} = 4.95$

$[Cd(Ox)_2(Pico)]^{2-}$: $\log \beta_{21} = 4.84$

The results of the present study have been conveniently summarised in the following diagram where the numerical values shown are the logarithms of equilibrium constants for the reactions indicated.

From the equilibrium constant values the tendency of a ligand to add to a complex and to substitute another ligand may be compared. The relative tendencies of Ox^{2-} and Pico to add to $[\text{Cd}(\text{Pico})]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{Pico})_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})_2]^{2-}$ respectively can be compared. It is seen that Ox^{2-} has a strong tendency to add to simple complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{Pico})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{Pico})_2]^{2+}$ to form mixed complexes as compared to β -picoline. Further, Ox^{2-} can replace β -picoline from its simple complexes. Thus, Ox^{2-} is a stronger ligand than β -picoline.

The mixing constant, K_m for the reaction

is given by :

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 (\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02})$$

and works out to be +1.1. The positive log value shows that the mixed complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pico})]$ is somewhat more stable than the simple binary complexes of Cd(II) with oxalate and picoline.

The equilibrium constants for the following disproportionation² reactions :

work out to be -2.2, -2.78 and -2.48, respectively. The large negative log values of the equilibrium constants indicate that the formation of mixed complexes is strongly favoured over the simple ones.

The stability of the three mixed complexes as seen from their overall stability constants follows the order $[\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pico})_2] > [\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{Pico})]^{2-} > [\text{Cd}(\text{Ox})(\text{Pico})]$.

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